
FREE-FLOAT AND STOCK LIQUIDITY: EVIDENCE FROM A POLICY EXPERIMENT

Mohammad Shameem Jawed^{a*}, Kiran Kumar Kotha^b and Vijay Kumar Gupta^b

^a Indian Institute of Management Visakhapatnam; Faculty Block B, Indian Institute of Management Visakhapatnam, Visakhapatnam, India - 530003 Email: msjawed@iimv.ac.in

ORCID ID: <http://orcid.org/0000-0003-0363-7683>

*Corresponding Author

^b Indian Institute of Management Indore, Indore, MP, India

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Abstract

On June 2010 the Securities and Exchange Board of India (SEBI) – the Indian market regulator, mandated the listed firms to increase their Minimum Public Shareholding (MPS) to 25%. Present study utilises this regulatory intervention as a natural experimental setup of an exogenous shock to free-floating stocks to examine the impact on stock liquidity. The study employs univariate Event Study and multivariate Difference-in-Difference regression analysis. Findings suggest that the MPS regulation significantly improved different stock liquidity measures and established the causality of stock free float to stock liquidity.

Keywords: Free-Float, Stock Liquidity, Minimum Public Shareholding, Difference-in-Difference.

Subject classification codes: G14, G18, G32.

1. Introduction

Stock liquidity has progressively become an important issue in the global capital markets. Though higher liquidity has been associated with the lower expected return, market regulators have been striving hard to improve it to eliminate more severe issues like price discovery, market manipulation, and minority shareholder protection. This study investigates the impact on stock liquidity from one such regulatory intervention by the Securities and Exchange Board of India (SEBI) in the year 2010–Minimum Public Shareholding (MPS)¹ that created an exogenous shock to the free-float in the market.

Free-float or public shareholding is defined as the outstanding stocks available for trading in the market that excludes shares held by insiders for control purposes.

¹ MPS regulation of India, like other developing markets (Philippines, Indonesia, Sri Lanka and Thailand), is intended to safeguard the venerable minority shareholders by increasing liquidity and price discovery process in such stocks. Firms were given three years to comply with the regulation. Non-adherence attracted severe penalties to the controlling stakeholders.

Extant literature suggests two broad mechanisms by which free-float may influence the stock liquidity on the bourses, viz., the 'free float' or the 'adverse selection' theories. According to the 'free float' hypothesis, it is believed that when there is frequent turnover in investors' portfolios, the average transaction cost decreases which, in turn, increases the stock liquidity (Stoll, 2000). On the contrary, as per the 'adverse selection' hypothesis which documents higher probability of informed trading when the ownership is concentrated. Thus, the liquidity providers widen the spread to accommodate the risk due to higher information asymmetry in such stocks. Since it is difficult to distinguish between informed and uninformed traders, we witness a reduction in liquidity in such stocks (Glosten and Milgrom, 1985).

However, the relationship between free-float and stock liquidity is more complex than these institutive theoretical arguments. Many market forces such as ownership structure (Bolton and Thadden, 1998), clientele (Ciner and Karagozoglu, 2008), information environment (Cao and Ou-Yang, 2009), regulatory and legal system (Brockman and Chung, 2003), and firm-specific characteristics (Gopinath and Krishnamurti, 2001) may play a vital role in determining the effective liquidity improvements as a result of the standard change in free-float. Thus, the best possible method to segregate the competing factors in explaining the true impact of improved free-float on stock liquidity shall be under exogenous shock to free-floating stocks.

One such attempt was made by Chan et al. (2004) using the Hong Kong government's intervention of buying 118.1 billion HKD worth of shares to decrease free-floating stocks as a natural experiment. Similarly, using instrument variables, Ding et al. (2016) found that stocks with higher free-float have better liquidity; however, the method used is not foolproof for establishing the causality.

This study has some unique contributions and departs from previous studies. First, the MPS regulation in India provides us with a natural experiment of increasing free-float, which impacted a larger diverse sample. Second, the MPS regulation impacted firms with relatively higher information asymmetry (concentrated insider ownership) compared to the firms impacted by the regulatory intervention in Hong Kong. Third, previous studies using a natural experimental setup captured intra-day changes in liquidity only, which may be very different from liquidity compositions in the medium to long run, as captured in this study. Fourth, this is a pioneering work to examines the impact of such regulatory intervention by the market regulator in emerging market setup, thus adding to the emerging cross-area literature emphasizing the important link between financial markets and corporate finance.

2. Indian Market & MPS Regulation

India is an emerging market economy with a very vibrant and large equity market. However, it is plagued by typical emerging market problems², along with issues that are unique and specific to the Indian institutional setup. In spite of having a robust regulatory framework of the listing laws (Clause 49), it is seen that the securities market regulator generally fails to efficiently police compliance in cases of insider trading, price manipulations, related-party transaction, and reporting and accounting frauds (Bose, 2005). The problem in the country is further compounded with a high proportion of family business leading to a higher concentration of Promoters (insiders/founders) with ownership proportions as high as ~50%³ (Claessens and Yurtoglu, 2013). The high concentration of insider ownership and weak enforcement of laws makes it easier for the promoters to expropriate the minority shareholders and also involve in direct or indirect stock price manipulations.

In view of these market imperfections and minority shareholder vulnerability arising from the high promoter holding in a number of stocks, SEBI in consultation with the Ministry of Finance, Government of India, came up with an amendment in Securities Contracts (Regulation) Rules (SCRR), 1956 on June 04, 2010⁴, for initial public offering and continued listing at Indian bourses. The regulation mandated all private-listed firms with a low free float to mandatorily increase it to 25% by the end of June 2013. Similarly, the minimum public float requirement for PSUs listed on the bourses was set at 10%, to be complied on or before August 2013. The regulatory move was in line with the global best practices of developed economies and the ongoing efforts of some emerging market economies.

2.1 MPS Regulation: The Chronology of Events

On June 04, 2010, the Ministry of Finance, GoI amended the Securities Contract (Regulation) Rules, 1956, vide Notification number GSR 469(E), which mandated all the listed firms on Indian bourses to ensure a minimum public shareholding of 25% (in all equity types) for initial and continued listing, on or before June 2013. Months later, it was amended on August 09, 2010 wherein the minimum public shareholding cap for the Public Sector firms was reduced to 10%, and the date for compliance was set as on or before August 2013, while the regulation in respect of deadline for bringing down the shareholding for the private listed firm remained unchanged.

The circular also specified that the public shareholding would not include the promoters, promoter groups, their subsidiaries associated with the company. It also excluded the depository receipts issued overseas from the public shareholding claims.

² See La Porta et al., 2000 for details.

³ 50.15%, 46% respectively for business group affiliates and Standalone private (Indian) firms

⁴ SEBI notified the firms on December 16, 2010, vide circular CIR/CFD/DIL/10/2010, which came under section 2(II) of the circular - Amendments to Clause 40A – Minimum public shareholding.

This move was in line with the global practices on a minimum public float in the developed capital markets. In the past 5-7 years, there had been instances of some developing Asian countries following the suit and making regulatory changes to ensure that the minimum public float in their stock markets also inches towards the best practices of the advanced stock exchanges globally.

2.2 Methods/Routes Specified by SEBI for Promoters' Equity Dilutions

SEBI wanted firms to dilute their promoter holding using Further Public Offering (FPO or SEO) only. This move was to ensure that the shares get distributed amongst a wider investor group. However, due to consistent request from the affected promoters and owing to the state of the secondary market, SEBI revised its earlier guidelines on January 03, 2012 & February 08, 2012, respectively and allowed two other channels of promoter share dilution namely OFS Window-Offer for Sale of Shares through recognized stock exchanges and IPP- Institutional Placement Program. This was further revised by SEBI on August 29, 2012-based on requests from firms which could not dilute their promoter holding in accordance with the specified guidelines. Thus, Bonus shares and Rights issuance were also included as methods of dilution. SEBI also mentioned that in cases where firms could not dilute their promoter holding by the specified methods, should submit options that they would like to undertake, which SEBI subsequently would evaluate and approve on a case-to-case basis.

3. Methodology

3.1. Data

Data was collected from the CMIE Prowess database for adjusted daily stock returns, ownership structure and other firm-specific financials. Equity dilution event dates are obtained from PRIME database. SEBI regulation to this effect for the listed firms came out on 16th December 2010, and the affected firms need to comply within a three-year period. Thus, we consider the calendar year 2010 as the pre-regulation and 2014 as the post-regulation year.

Out of the 286 firms, 157 complied with the provisions of the regulation within the stipulated window. Of these 157 firms, 15 chose to delist using the Reverse book building method, while eight firms amalgamated with their parent company. The remaining 134 companies formed our sample. However, we dropped 22 firms from the analysis that was either traded for less than 100 days in a year or had missing financial data.

3.2 Empirical framework

We start our empirical examination with a univariate analysis of possible significant changes in the liquidity variables in the event study framework.

We calculate the daily price-impact (AMIHUD and HUANG) and volumetric (TURNOVER) (il) liquidity and average them for one year, both before and after the regulation adherence window.

Further, to rule out the possibility of other temporal market-wide factors resulting in improved stock liquidity and to establish the causality of free-float to stock liquidity, we further perform a Difference-in-Difference regression analysis, as suggested in Villa (2016).

$$(II) \text{liquidity}_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot \text{period}_i + \beta_2 \cdot \text{treated}_i + \beta_3 \cdot \text{period}_i \cdot \text{treated}_i + \beta_k \cdot X_{k,t} + \epsilon_i$$

Where;

$\widehat{\beta}_3$ = Difference-in-Difference (treated-control) which captures the treatment effect
 $X_{k,i}$ = k^{th} control variable or observable characteristics and $\widehat{\beta}_k$ are their respective coefficients

period_i = a dummy variable which takes a value of 0 for the baseline and 1 for the follow-up time period for the i^{th} firm

treated_i = a dummy variable which takes a value of 0 for the i^{th} firm in the control group and 1 for the treatment group firms.

The affected firms (treatment group) were compared with a matched group of firms (control group, selected via propensity score matching), which remained unaffected by the regulation.

3.3. Variables

3.3.1 Liquidity Measures

Goyenko et al., (2009) illustrated the need for using multiple measures to capture different liquidity dimensions. We primarily capture the resilience by Amihud's return to volumetric measure (2002), which measures the price impact of trade. Among the different price impact proxies, Goyenko et al., (2009) report that Amihud measure of illiquidity is generally the best candidate. Amihud Illiquidity measure is calculated as the annual average of daily illiquidity measures which is the ratio of absolute daily stock return to rupee volume of the trade (average trading price multiplied by the respective daily trading volume). We then scale up the values by multiplying them with 1000 for easy handling for calculations.

The breadth of stock liquidity is captured by Turnover which is calculated as the daily number of shares traded (volume) as a percentage of the number of shares

outstanding on the day (shares out), averaged over the number of trading days (n) in the preceding 12 months. Due to unavailability of the high-frequency trade data, we could not use many other available liquidity measures and restrict to Turnover as the main variable of interest for capturing the volume-based liquidity change following the suggestions from the research works of Jun et al. (2003) and Bekaert et al., (2007). Moreover, Korajczyk and Sadka (2008) in their research work, find that Turnover ratio is one of the most suitable measures of liquidity for emerging market context amongst the eight commonly used liquidity proxies.

In addition to Amihud Illiquidity and stock Turnover, we also measure the change in liquidity by Huang Illiquidity measure for robustness. Given that the study has been conducted on firms in an emerging market, we include the Huang measure of illiquidity, which considers the effect of the turnover rate of stock on its price amplitude. Huang (2009) argues that the essence of measuring illiquidity is to look at how trading activities affect the stock price. In contrast, Amihud's ratio uses the daily price return to indicate such influence which has noticeable estimation error. The reason is that using daily price return as a measure of price change also involves price change caused by non-trading factors during the non-trading hours of stock (i.e., the time between the opening and previous day's closing). In fact, several factors can cause stock's opening price to be different from the previous day's closing price (either higher, lower or a price gap-commonly known as gap-up opening). For example, news of issuing a positive earnings announcement or news regarding the fundamental variation in the value of a corporation, among others, are some of the causative factors for price variations. Using price amplitude to measure price movements would allow us to observe price changes due to the aforesaid factors before the non-trading hours of stock and after the opening of stock, which subtly avoids price movements accounted for by non-trading factors. Also, considering the higher discrepancy between outstanding shares and issued shares on emerging stock markets, Huang aptly suggests that using stock turnover rate instead of trading volume would be more suitable for determining the market illiquidity Li and Hong (2013).

According to Li and Hong (2013) Huang measure of illiquidity, which considers the effect of the turnover rate of stock on its price amplitude is more apt for emerging markets where due to higher information asymmetry stocks opening price have a higher deviation from the previous day's close (gap-up opening due to information accumulated in non-trading hours).

3.3.2. Control Variables

Stock liquidity is a function comprising many known and unknown factors. We have tried to control some important parameters, as detailed below, that are reported in the literature to have an impact on stock liquidity.

Institutional Ownership is captured as level and calculated as the annual percentage of institutional ownership averaged over the quarterly ownership data of stocks for a given calendar year. Extant literature has empirically established positive and significant correlation between institutional ownership and stock liquidity, especially in the emerging market's context (Agarwal, 2007; Dang et al., 2018; Cao & Petrasek, 2014; among others).

Annual Returns (momentum) is calculated as the calendar year's accumulated daily returns data for the stock. Previous studies control for momentum effect while studying the stock liquidity (Agarwal et al., 2015; Ali et al., 2017, among others)

Volatility is an annual variance of the daily returns as a proxy for stock volatility. Like momentum, stock volatility is also well documented in literature to have impact on stock liquidity (Agarwal et al., 2015; Lesmond, 2005, among others).

Price-to-Book Ratio is the annual average of the daily stock PB ratio. This captures the firm's growth prospects. Extant literature document that high growth firms are expected to be subjected to higher information asymmetry (Agarwal et al., 2015; Hutchinson & Gul, 2004, among others)

Inv_Price is the inverse of the average annual stock price. Extant literature on stock liquidity control for the inverse of stock price to control for the tick size effect which has been documented to have implications on stock liquidity (Agarwal et al., 2015; Ali et al., 2017; Prommin et al., 2014, among others).

Ln_Size is the natural logarithm of the annual average of quarterly data on the firm's total asset, which is also well documented as an important firm characteristic to control for in stock liquidity studies, as larger firms experience smaller adverse selection risk (Agarwal et al., 2015; Anderson, 1996; Chung et al., 2010, among others).

4. Results and Discussion

Table 1 reports the t-test results for change in liquidity. We observe that the HUANG Illiquidity values decreased by 65.67% (at $p < 0.05$) while comparing the average annual illiquidity values of one-year pre and post equity dilution by promoters. Similarly, the TURNOVER improved by 160.7% ($p < 0.01$) in the average value of one-year post-equity dilution. Thus, we find that the overall liquidity of the affected firms improved due to the improved free float resulting from equity sale by promoters.

Table-1: Univariate Analysis

The table reports the change in - Stock Liquidity (After-Before) Ho: Mean difference is zero.

Variables	Mean (After-Before)
	Stock Liquidity
AMIHUD (Illiquidity)	-0.2942
HUANG (Illiquidity)	-0.4204**
TUNROVER (Liquidity)	0.4744***

*** $p < 0.01$; ** $p < 0.05$;

Up next, to establish the causality of free float to stock liquidity, we conducted the DiD regression analysis. Since Stock liquidity is a function comprising many known and unknown factors, we control for variables that are reported in the literature to have an impact on stock liquidity. These are Annual Stock Return (Momentum), Return Volatility, log of Size, the inverse of Share Price, Price-to-Book ratio, and institutional holding.

We conduct the DiD regression analysis for all the firms that adhered to the regulation window, making 2010-2014 our effective sample period. The detailed results of the DiD analysis are tabulated in Table 2.

Table-2: DiD regression results – Stock Liquidity

The table below reports the Difference-in-Difference regression analysis conducted using Eq.(i)., where Column (1-3) shows the result AMIHUD, HUANG and TURNOVER respectively. The values in parenthesis () reports the Std. Error while t-statistics are denoted by *** $p < 0.01$; ** $p < 0.05$; * $p < 0.1$ and square brackets [] report z-statistics.

	(1)	(2)	(3)
Control Variables			
Institutional Ownership (%)	-0.053 [-4.08]	-0.056 [-4.25]	-.0532 [-4.08]
Log (Size)	0.005 [0.13]	0.006 [0.15]	.0056 [0.13]
Annual Returns (Momentum)	-21.143 [-0.91]	-17.06 [-0.60]	-21.1435 [-0.91]
Price-to-Book Ratio	0.0013 [0.71]	0.0013 [0.74]	.00132 [0.71]
Inverse of Annual Average Stock Price	-1.337 [-0.51]	-0.912 [-0.34]	-1.3379 [-0.51]
Average Annual Variance of Returns (Volatility)	-26.479 [-2.29]	-34.132 [-2.72]	-26.4798 [-2.29]
Difference-in-Difference Statistics			
Coefficient of Difference at Baseline (Treatment-Control)	0.768* (0.407)	0.534*** (0.191)	-0.901*** (0.155)
Coefficient of Difference at Follow-Up (Treatment-Control)	-0.796* (0.407)	-0.038 (0.191)	-0.420*** (0.155)
Difference-in-Difference (Diff of Follow-Up - Diff of Baseline)	-1.564*** (0.575)	-0.572** (0.270)	0.480** (0.219)
R Square of the Model	0.13	0.15	0.22

Column 1, 2 and 3 shows the parameter estimates of DiD regression for AMIHUUD, HUANG and TURNOVER, respectively. The treatment effect (DiD) coefficient β_3 in Eq.(i) is the coefficient of interest. Since we have used the log-transformed values of (il) liquidity for the analysis, the coefficient is interpreted as the percentage change in (il) liquidity values, given by $[100*\{\exp(\beta_3)-1\}]$. We find that the illiquidity values AMIHUUD and HUNAG show a significant decrease of 79.07 and 43.56 percentage points at $p < 0.01$ & 0.05 , respectively, suggesting a substantial increase in the stock liquidity of the treatment group. Similarly, TURNOVER shows a 61.6% increase from the pre-regulation period for the treatment firms (at $p < 0.5$), signifying a significant jump in stock liquidity (market depth) of the treatment firms. Thus, we can conclude that we could establish the causality between free-float and stock liquidity under an exogenous shock to free-floating stocks caused by MPS regulation.

5. Conclusion

The present study examines the impact of the increased free float resulting from the forced sale of equity by promoters to non-promoters on stocks' liquidity. The sale was mandated by the securities market regulator in India in 2010 for listed firms under the MPS regulation. We also utilize this unique natural experiment to test the causality between free-float and stock liquidity. While confirming the causal relationship, the results indicate that such regulatory moves effectively improve stock liquidity. This is an encouraging outcome for all emerging market regulators who are grappled with market imperfections caused by very high insider ownership, and such a forced measure could result in improved liquidity resulting in better price discovery by improved institutional investor participation and indirect monitoring and governance via trading and exit.

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